

SUSTAINABLE ALIGNED SHORT CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH ELECTROSPUN POLYMER MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

Aligned short fibre composites have demonstrated exceptional tensile strength, stiffness, and load-bearing capabilities, as evidenced by both theoretical and experimental [1, 2] studies over the past decade, establishing them as a promising material for future advanced applications. Additionally, they provide an opportunity to better utilise recycled fibres, further promoting sustainability in composite materials. Short fiber alignment techniques, such as HiPerDiF [2] and TuFF [3], produce dry preforms that must be combined with a resin system. The most effective method to fabricate composites with aligned fibres involves stacking epoxy resin films with aligned fibre preforms, followed by compression using autoclave vacuum bag moulding. Another approach has been to use resin infusion processes with infusible epoxy resin or thermoplastic (Elium®) resin systems. Though they have shown great success in proving superior mechanical properties, challenges remain: 1) thermoset resin systems are difficult to recycle, and 2) there is limited understanding of how the resin combining process affects the structural integrity of aligned fibre assemblies during fabrication. This study therefore investigates the role of matrix material and its microstructure in composites fabricated with aligned carbon fibres by comparing two distinct matrices: electrospun thermoplastic polymer and conventionally fabricated polymer films. The electrospun polymer matrix features a fine, partially aligned fiber architecture and a high surface area, enhancing fiber-matrix impregnation unlike conventional polymer films. Both composite configurations are fabricated with aligned carbon fibres and subjected to mechanical testing, including tensile properties, to evaluate their performance. This paper highlights the potential of leveraging advanced matrix fabrication techniques to maximise the mechanical advantages offered by aligned carbon fibres, paving the way for lightweight, high-performance composite materials suitable for engineering and aerospace applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Highly aligned discontinuous fibre composites have drawn attention not only for their comparable stiffness and strength to continuous fibre composites [4], but also for their formability and recyclability. Several methods have been developed to produce such composites, e.g., HiPerDiF [5], rotating drum [6] and TuFF [7].

Studies show that the mechanical performance of the composite increases with greater fibre alignment [2, 5, 8]. In addition to improved mechanical properties, manufacturing complex parts with aligned discontinuous fibre is easier, as the fibres can adjust their position during forming, preventing buckling and wrinkling [7, 9]. Also, aligned discontinuous fibre composites possess some level of ductility, making them a suitable choice for applications that require pseudo-ductile materials [10]. Most importantly, the greatest potential of aligned discontinuous fibre composites is their ability to

support recyclability. Fibres reclaimed after their lifecycle in applications can be used to produce new aligned discontinuous fibre composites. In this way, recycled fibres are utilised in higher-value materials, supporting a circular economy and reducing landfill waste [4]. Case studies and application prototypes, such as flexi wings on formula 1 car, tennis rackets, provide good examples of this potential [11].

However, to take full advantage of the recyclability of aligned discontinuous fibre composites, thermoplastic type polymer is preferred over thermoset type polymer [12]. Thermoplastics, however, have higher melt viscosities, which lead to insufficient impregnation of the fibre bundles [13]. Poor impregnation results in inefficient load transfer between the fibres and matrix [14], reducing the overall strength of the composite.

One approach to improving impregnation is to use the electrospun form of thermoplastic polymers. Electrospun thermoplastic polymer sheets have higher porosity and surface area than conventional films, which can enhance impregnation [15]. Using electrospun polymer sheets in aligned short fibre composites offers additional benefits beyond improved impregnation. One such benefit is that electrospun sheets exhibit a unique structure, with nano/micro-fibres partially aligned in a single direction. This, combined with their porosity, could help retain fibre alignment during compression moulding. Moreover, this is particularly beneficial when using HiPerDiF or TuFF processes to produce aligned fibre preforms, as these methods may leave a small amount of moisture after fibre alignment. The porous structure of electrospun sheets can help remove this moisture effectively.

This study attempts to use electrospun thermoplastic polymer material as a matrix in manufacturing aligned short carbon fibre composites, in order to compare them with conventional aligned short carbon fibre composites. Aligned short carbon fibres are combined with two types of PLA material: i) Conventional PLA film and ii) Electrospun PLA film, to form composites whose tensile properties are then compared.

2 ALIGNED SHORT CARBON FIBRES

An experimental setup was developed to prepare aligned carbon fibre preforms. This setup is based on the principle of HiPerDiF method [2], which uses a sudden change in momentum of a fibre-water suspension onto a plate to align the fibres. The fibre alignment head consists of thin parallel plates that capture the fibre-water suspension jets. Below the head is a moving conveyor belt, which collects the aligned fibres and allows the water drain out, resulting in an aligned fibre preform on the belt. This setup is of smaller size than HiPerDiF and can generate a preform of around 5 mm in width. 3 mm length of carbon fibres (Tenax-A HT C124- 3 mm [16]) were used in this study which resulted in an aspect ratio of around 428. To assess the alignment of fibres in a preform, the Rapid Fibre Alignment Assessment (RFAA) method was adopted [17, 18]. To apply this method (See Figure 1), a section of preform was first imaged. The whole image was then sectioned into equally spaced, same-sized 'Region Of Interest (ROI)'. This code was applied to each ROI individually. Based on the defined formula, the image in each ROI was transformed in the x and y directions, and the transformed image was then subtracted from the original image. The resultant pixel density in x and y directions after subtraction indicated the fibre alignment in each ROI.

This method is quicker and effective [18, 19]. The RFAA method was applied to five images of the dry preforms before they were combining with the resin matrix, and the mean fibre alignment was found to be ± 8 deg.

Figure 1: (a) Aligned fibres image, (b) Segmented into small region of interest (ROI), and (c) Applied RFAA method to assess alignment in each ROI

3 PLA MATERIAL AS MATRIX

The conventional PLA film was obtained from Goodfellow, Cambridge UK (product: ME34-FM-000100). This film has a thickness of 0.05 mm, with a tensile strength of 53 MPa and a tensile modulus of 3.5 GPa. For electrospun PLA, granules were acquired from the same manufacturer and have similar mechanical properties. These granules were then dissolved in chloroform and dimethylformamide, and stirred for 4 hours at 50° C to produce a PLA solution. This solution was then fed through a syringe, where it was stretched and deposited as a porous film (containing PLA micro-fibers) onto a collector, similar to a typical electrospinning process [20], except that a roller type collector was used instead of a flat one. Since the roller rotates at a constant speed, the deposited micro-fibers are aligned in the direction of rotation. A voltage of 25 kV was applied between the syringe and the collector, and with the collector rotating at 3500 RPM, a 20 µm thick, porous film containing PLA micro-fibers was formed.

Figure 2. (a) Typical Electrospinning set-up, (b) Electrospinning setup with roller collector and (c) micro-fibres of PLA in electrospun film.

4 TENSILE TEST SAMPLE PREPARATION

Two sets of samples were prepared: one using conventional PLA film and the other using electrospun PLA sheets, and tensile tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D3039 standards. In both cases, the same number of dry aligned carbon fibre preform layers (eight in total) was used. To achieve a consistent fibre volume fraction of approximately 23%, the preforms were stacked differently according to the stacking sequence as follows:

For conventional PLA - P + aligned carbon fibre - f :

$$[P/f]_s$$

For electrospun PLA - EP + aligned carbon fibre - f :

$$[EP_s/[f/EP]_4/EP/[EP/f]_4/EP_s]$$

These stacked layers were subjected to compression moulding by vacuum bagging and then placed in an oven. The pressure and temperature were set to 1 bar and 200° C, respectively. The samples measured 5 mm in width, 150 mm in length and 0.2 mm in thickness. Conventional PLA required 30 mins at 200°C to form composites, while electrospun PLA formed composites in 20 mins at the same temperature (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Heating cycle for electrospun and conventional PLA composites (Note: Constant vacuum applied.)

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three specimens were tested in each sample set using a tensile testing machine (Instron D5967, 30 kN load cell). The results are shown in Figure 4. The use of electrospun PLA as a matrix resulted in a meaningful increase in mechanical properties compared to conventional PLA film. The tensile strength increased from 285 MPa to 337 MPa, an improvement of approximately 18%. Likewise, the tensile

modulus rose from 17.6 GPa to 19 GPa, reflecting an increase of about 8.0%. These results show that electrospun PLA can contribute to enhancing the mechanical performance of aligned short fibre composites. This can be attribute to more uniform and thermal behaviour of electrospun film. Due to its fine fibre structure, it heats and melts evenly and quickly. Also, it's higher surface area due to fine fibre structure helps it to flow more effectively between fibre bundles without affecting fibre alignment, resulting in good impregnation. In contrast, the conventional PLA film with its lower thermal responsiveness results in incomplete impregnation and its lower surface area may disrupt fibre alignment.

Figure 4. Tensile strength and modulus between electrospun and conventional PLA composites with aligned discontinuous carbon fibres.

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this study, a simple comparison was made between the tensile properties of composites manufactured from two different forms of PLA. The conventional PLA film and electrospun PLA film were compression moulded with aligned short carbon fibres for 30 mins and 20 mins respectively, at 200° C. The results show that the electrospun PLA composite achieved higher tensile modulus and tensile strength than the conventional PLA composite, despite requiring less processing time. Therefore, using the electrospun form of the thermoplastic matrix material could be a potential solution for improving the sustainability of carbon fibre composites. This is largely attributed to its better impregnation capability, which leads to fewer defects during processing. The fine fibre structure and porosity of the electrospun PLA allow the matrix to flow more efficiently between the carbon fibre bundles, reducing voids and enhancing composite quality with shorter moulding times.

However, further research is needed to fully understand the effects of the moulding process on fibre alignment. The high viscosity of melted PLA can disrupt the alignment and structure of the carbon fibre preforms during processing. This disruption is expected to be less significant when using electrospun PLA, due to its porous structure and fine fibre morphology, which promote more uniform melting and better flow. Ongoing studies aim to investigate how these characteristics influence fibre alignment during composite fabrication.

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